

stretchBIO

D2.1 – Report on relation deformation-force for the nanopillars

StretchBio – D2.1

Identifier:	StretchBio_D.2.1_Report on relation deformation-force for the nanopillars
Work package:	WP 2
Dissemination level:	Public
Keywords:	Nanopillar, deformation, stress, forces, finite-elements-method
Abstract:	This deliverable presents the results of the relation between nanopillars deformation and horizontally exerted forces simulated by the finite element method. It reports the values corresponding to different nanopillar vertical and radial dimensions, corresponding to the dimensions which can be fabricated. These values are relevant for selecting the subsequent fabrication processes in the frame of StretchBio project.

Document history:

Version	Date	Reason of change
1	09/02/2022	Creation of document
1.1	25/03/2022	Complete draft
1.2	03/03/2022	Deliverable review and validation by Coordinator
1.3	06/03/2022	Final version

Document author(s):

Entity	Contributor
DTU	Maria Dimaki
DTU	Christian Bertelsen
UB-IN2UB	Daniel Navarro Urrios
UB-IN2UB	Mauricio Moreno Sereno
UB-IN2UB	Elena López Aymerich
UB-IN2UB	Juliana Jaramillo Fernández
UB-IN2UB	Albert Romano Rodríguez
UB-IN2UB	Francisco Hernández

Disclosure Statement:

This document has been produced by consortium partners of the *StretchBio* Horizon 2020 project, funded by the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No. 964808. The content of this document, the information contained herein, and the views expressed are those of the authors and do not necessarily reflect the official opinion of the European Union. Neither the European Union institutions and bodies nor any person acting on their behalf may be held responsible for the use which may be made of the information contained.

Executive Summary

This deliverable presents the results of the relation between nanopillar deformation and horizontally exerted forces simulated by the finite element method. It reports the values corresponding to different nanopillar vertical and radial dimensions, corresponding to the dimensions which can be fabricated with nowadays available technologies. These values are relevant for selecting the subsequent fabrication route and its associated processes to be developed in the next stages of StretchBio project.

The obtained results show that nanopillar horizontal displacements larger than 10 nanometers are expected for forces in the range of nano Newton, pillars radius below 50 nanometers and pillar heights above 1 micrometer.

Table of Contents

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY	3
1 INTRODUCTION	7
1.1 PURPOSE OF THE DOCUMENT	7
1.2 SCOPE OF THE DOCUMENT	8
1.3 RELATED DOCUMENTS	8
2 PILLAR BENDING	9
2.1 THEORY (EQUATIONS, YOUNG’S MODULUS, ETC.)	9
2.2 ASSUMPTIONS AND MODEL SETUP	10
3 RESULTS.....	12
3.1 SIMPLE PILLAR BENDING	12
3.2 COMPOSITE PILLARS	15
3.3 EFFECT OF SUBSTRATE ON MAXIMUM DISPLACEMENT.....	16
3.4 SILICON ANISOTROPY	18
3.5 PILLAR STRESS.....	19
4 CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE WORK	21
GLOSSARY.....	22
ANNEX 1: ANISOTROPY OF SILICON.....	23

List of Figures

Figure 1: Tip deflection as a function of applied force for a pillar with a radius of 45 nm and a height of 400, 800 and 1200 nm.	10
Figure 2. Sketch of the three simulated configurations: a) Silicon pillar without simulated substrate, b) composite pillar consisting of silicon and silicon oxide without simulated substrate, c) silicon pillar with simulated silicon oxide substrate.	11
Figure 3. Displacement vs pillar radius for an applied force of 15 nN.....	12
Figure 4. Displacement vs pillar radius for an applied force of 30 nN.....	13
Figure 5. Displacement vs pillar radius for an applied force of 45 nN.....	13
Figure 6. Maximum displacement as a function of applied force for a silicon pillar of 45 nm radius at four pillar heights.	14
Figure 7. Deflection vs. applied force for pillars of three different heights, two different Young's moduli, as calculated theoretically and simulated numerically.....	14
Figure 8. Maximum displacement of 1.8- μ m tall pillars made from silicon oxide/silicon as a function of the applied force for three different radius values.	15
Figure 9. Maximum displacement of 1.8- μ m tall pillars made from silicon oxide/silicon & Si	16
Figure 10. Bending profile along the height of the pillar for the 1.8 μ m tall pillars	16
Figure 11. The displacement of the pillar as a function of pillar radius, pillar height and force applied.	17
Figure 12. Maximum displacement for a pillar of 45nm in radius with a height of 1.2 μ m and 1.8 μ m.....	18
Figure 13. Pillar displacement as a function of bending angle for two different force magnitudes (15 nN and 30 nN)	18
Figure 14. Spatial distribution of the von Mises Stress around the base of the pillar.	19
Figure 15. Maximum von Mises stress for different pillar dimensions and applied forces.....	20
Figure 16. Polar plot of the Young's modulus of silicon as a function of bending angle.	23

List Tables

Table 1. Second moment of inertia of pillars with different cross-section geometries	9
Table 2. Displacement in nm for three selected pillar radii and four pillar heights (F=15 nN)	21

1 Introduction

1.1 Purpose of the document

This report is written as the first deliverable for WP2 (D2.1), and it presents the initial theoretical findings of the mechanical bending of the nanopillars in the proposed sensor system. For details on the overall purpose, we refer to the project description given in the grant agreement.

A final device design needs to consider all technical areas (mechanical feasibility, optical feasibility, biological feasibility, and feasibility of fabrication). However, since we are in the first stages of the project, there are still many open questions regarding the sensor system. For example, it is not yet known how large the deformation of the pillar needs to be for leading to a measurable variation in the optical properties.

The deliverable gives an overview of the mechanical characteristics of nanopillars and will act as a guideline for future nanosensor design decisions. It aims to give all participants in the project an introduction to the bending mechanics so that they can make decisions within their field of expertise, while still considering the feasibility of the proposed solution from a mechanical point of view.

As such, this report attempts to answer the following open questions:

- Which is the theoretical relationship between horizontal force and bending deformation of a nanopillar?
- How does the magnitude of the deformation depend on the dimensions (height and radius) of the pillar?
- How will the material properties of the pillar affect the deformation?
- What are the reasonable limits of height and radius that can be recommended for the nanosensor system fabrication from a mechanical point of view?

We have used the linear elasticity theory and the structural mechanics module of *COMSOL Multiphysics*¹ to answer the above questions.

To move forward, the simple situation of a single isotropic pillar was first assumed and then pillars of different materials as well as anisotropic materials were explored. The output from this work includes force-displacement curves for a range of different pillar parameters and theoretical consideration of the influence of crystal orientations in the mechanical properties.

The COMSOL models developed can be used in the future to simulate other geometries that might need to be required at later stages of the project.

¹ <https://www.comsol.com/>

1.2 Scope of the document

This report includes:

- A description of the theoretical approach to the mechanics of bending pillars;
- A discussion of the material properties of the pillars and their influence on the bending;
- A presentation of several finite element simulations that show the relationship between the bending force and the subsequent deformation for pillars of different dimensions.

In summary, here we show that pillars of radius below 50 nm and a height of at least 1.2 μm , made entirely of silicon, can bend more than 10 nm for applied forces over 15 nN. This is assumed to be the minimal deflection to could induce a signal difference in a photonic crystal, but it will depend on the photonic crystal geometry, which is a topic currently under investigation. From previous experience, we believe that any displacement smaller than 10 nm will not give enough signal differences in the photonic crystal, which is why this limit was chosen for the here-presented work.

At the same time, pillars with radii above 80 nm are rigid and will bend very little. Therefore, applying forces to them will not result in a significant deformation, which will not disturb the light management properties of the photonic crystal. Moreover, we show that pillars made of composite materials (silicon dioxide base and silicon top) will exhibit larger displacements.

Finally, we show that the bending depends on the applied force direction relative to the crystallographic plane.

1.3 Related documents

The report provides input for future work regarding the suitable geometry of the nanopillars composing the photonic crystal nanosensor. It will be a reference for the remaining work to be carried out in WP2, WP3, WP4 and WP6 (to be presented in D2.2 to D2.4, D3.1 to D3.5, D4.1, D.4.2 and from D6.1 to D6.5).

2 Pillar Bending

This section introduces the basic principles and theory used to understand the mechanical bending of a pillar.

2.1 Theory (Equations, Young's Modulus, etc.)

The deflection of a pillar under a force load (F) is described by linear elasticity theory in the following way

$$F = \frac{3EI}{L^3} \Delta x$$

where E is Young's modulus, I is the second moment of inertia, L is the length (i.e. height) of the pillar, and Δx is the displacement of the tip of the pillar.

The second moment of inertia (I) depends on the cross-sectional geometry of the pillar. Some common expressions for I for different geometries are shown in Table 1².

Geometry	Filled circle	Filled ellipse	Filled rectangle	Filled hexagonal
Figure				
2 nd moment of inertia	$I_x = I_y = \frac{\pi}{4} r^4$	$I_x = \frac{\pi}{4} ab^3, I_y = \frac{\pi}{4} a^3b$	$I_x = \frac{bh^3}{12}, I_y = \frac{b^3h}{12}$	$I_x = I_y = \frac{5\sqrt{3}}{16} a^4$

Table 1: Second moment of inertia of pillars with different cross-section geometries

We expect the cross-sectional geometry of the pillars used in this project to be circular and the tip deflection can therefore be calculated using

$$F = \frac{3EI}{L^3} \Delta x = \frac{3\pi}{4} \times \frac{Er^4}{L^3} \Delta x$$

where r is the radius of the pillar.

Using this equation, the tip deflection of a nanopillar with $E=170$ GPa, which is the Young modulus of silicon material, as a function of the applied force can be calculated and plotted, as seen in Figure.

² https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/List_of_second_moments_of_area

Figure 1: Tip deflection as a function of applied force for a pillar with a radius of 45 nm and a height of 400, 800 and 1200 nm. Young's modulus for all pillars is 170 GPa.

2.2 Assumptions and model setup

We assume that the force that the tissue placed on top of the pillar will exert on it is applied to the top boundary and in a direction perpendicular to the pillar's top surface. Based on studies of cellular forces³, we can expect forces of the order of tens of nN exerted on the pillars. So, we have based all calculations and simulations on forces varying between 0 and 100 nN.

Silicon is an anisotropic material, meaning that the Young's modulus varies as a function of the crystallographic plane. This means that the maximum displacement of the pillar depends on the bending angle relative to a specific crystallographic plane. We have therefore taken into account the expected Young's modulus as a function of the angle of the applied force relative to the x -axis. Here, we assume that we have a [100] silicon wafer so that the top surface of the pillar is the (100) plane.

Besides, we have further changed the pillar composition so that it consists of a silicon oxide part with a height of 1 μm and a silicon part on top, with a height of 800 nm. For these simulations we assume that both materials are isotropic, with a Young's modulus of 70 GPa and 170 GPa⁴, respectively. The bending was compared to that of a homogeneous silicon pillar of a total height of 1.8 μm .

Finally, we have explored the influence of the substrate on the pillar bending, by adding a silicon oxide substrate beneath the pillar and allowing the surrounding area to move.

A schematic depicting the different configurations is shown in Figure 2.

³ Z. Li et al., "Cellular traction forces: a useful parameter in cancer research," *Nanoscale*, vol. 9, no. 48, pp. 19039–19044, 2017, doi: [10.1039/C7NR06284B](https://doi.org/10.1039/C7NR06284B).

⁴ From COMSOLs built-in material library, for Silicon Oxide and Silicon respectively

D2.1 – Report on relation deformation-force for the nanopillars

Figure 2. Sketch of the three simulated configurations: a) Silicon pillar without simulated substrate, b) composite pillar consisting of silicon and silicon oxide without simulated substrate, c) silicon pillar with simulated silicon oxide substrate. Arrows indicated the application point of the force. Black lines indicate where the model is constricted (i.e., where it will not move when under load).

3 Results

Several different simulations have been conducted to investigate if the force exerted by the attached tissue will bend a pillar and under which conditions that will happen.

We use COMSOL Multiphysics version 6.0 on a desktop computer, running Windows 10 and specifically the Solid Mechanics module. The materials are selected from COMSOL's material library. The pillar base is assumed to be fixed onto a substrate and a boundary load is applied to the top surface of the pillar.

Although silicon is an anisotropic material, we have conducted most simulations considering silicon to be isotropic. We have, however, looked at changes due to anisotropy in Young's modulus from 130 GPa to 170 GPa and checked that for the lowest value of E , larger displacements are induced by a 30 nN applied force, but the differences are less than 1 nm, which can be considered negligible.

3.1 Simple pillar bending

Forces of 15 nN, 30 nN and 45 nN were applied on pillars of four different heights, namely 400 nm, 800 nm, 1200 nm and 1800 nm, and for radii varying from 45 nm to 295 nm. Silicon was treated as an isotropic material with Young's module of 170 GPa. The results are shown in Figures 3 to 5.

Figure 3. Displacement vs pillar radius for an applied force of 15 nN

Figure 4. Displacement vs pillar radius for an applied force of 30 nN

Figure 5. Displacement vs pillar radius for an applied force of 45 nN

Figures 3 to 5 show that displacements larger than 10 nm are obtained in pillars with radius below 60 nm and heights above 800 nm.

We can also see from the figures that any pillars with radii above 80 nm will, at best move less than 10 nm by the expected force from the tissue, which means that such pillars can be used as the body of the photonic crystal. In simple words, this indicates that we do not expect that the movement of pillars larger than 80 nm in radius will change the light propagation properties of the photonic crystal.

Having established that we need a pillar of small radius for potentially achieving a measurable signal, we have also looked at the displacement as a function of force for different pillar heights, while keeping the pillar radius at 45 nm.

D2.1 – Report on relation deformation-force for the nanopillars

Since forces exerted by cells are of the order of nN⁵, we vary the applied forces in our simulations from 1 to 30 nN. From figures 2 and 3 it can be observed that further increasing the force does not result in large changes in the deflection. The results are shown in Figure 6.

Figure 6. Maximum displacement as a function of applied force for a silicon pillar of 45 nm radius at four pillar heights.

From Figure 6 we can conclude that pillars of 1200 nm and 1800 nm height will experience displacement that is large enough to be measured. Next, we have compared the simulation results to the theoretical values (based on the equation in section 2.1). This is plotted in Figure 7, wherefrom we can conclude that there is a good correlation between simulation and theory, particularly for pillars of 800 nm height or taller.

Figure 7. Deflection vs. applied force for pillars of three different heights, two different Young's moduli, as calculated theoretically and simulated numerically

⁵ Z. Li et al., "Cellular traction forces: a useful parameter in cancer research," *Nanoscale*, vol. 9, no. 48, pp. 19039–19044, 2017, doi: [10.1039/C7NR06284B](https://doi.org/10.1039/C7NR06284B).

3.2 Composite pillars

Keeping in mind that for photonic applications the silicon pillars need to be embedded between two lower refraction index materials to give rise to light guidance, and that the lower one is silicon oxide, we might benefit from extending the pillars into the underlying insulator. Therefore, we looked at the possibility of fabricating pillars that consist of two materials, a bottom part made of silicon oxide and a top part of silicon.

Silicon oxide has a lower Young's module of 70 GPa compared to silicon. Therefore, we expect that the presence of silicon oxide at the bottom will lead to a larger deflection of the pillar. Figure 8 shows the displacement of the tip of the pillar as a function of the applied force for radius values of 45, 100 and 160 nm.

We compared a 1.8 μm silicon pillar to a silicon oxide/silicon pillar of the same height, where the bottom 1 μm was silicon oxide and the top 800 nm were silicon (configuration b in Scheme 1). The resulting deflection as a function of force, for a 45 nm radius pillar, is shown in Figure 9. The bending profile of the pillars along the pillar height for a force of 20 nN is shown in Figure 10.

The composite pillar has a much larger deflection than the pure silicon one, e.g., for a force of 20 nN the silicon pillar has a deflection of 71 nm vs 163 nm for the silicon oxide/silicon pillar.

Apart from the larger maximum deflection, the composite silicon oxide/silicon pillar also has a larger displacement at every point along with the pillar height compared to the silicon pillar, as shown in Figure 10.

Figure 8. Maximum displacement of 1.8 μm tall pillars made from silicon oxide/silicon as a function of the applied force for three different radius values.

Figure 9. Maximum displacement of 1.8 μm tall pillars made from silicon oxide/silicon and silicon

Figure 10. Bending profile along the height of the pillar for the 1.8 μm tall pillars

3.3 Effect of substrate on maximum displacement

So far, we have simulated the pillar as an independent entity. However, the pillar is on a silicon oxide substrate, which could influence the bending magnitude but also the stress, particularly at the interface area. The geometry used for these simulations is that of panel c of Figure 2.

As in the previous sections, we varied the radius and height of the pillars, as well as the force applied on the top boundary. The results are summarized in Figure 11.

D2.1 – Report on relation deformation-force for the nanopillars

Figure 11. The displacement of the pillar as a function of pillar radius, pillar height and force applied. The threshold for pillar displacements larger than 10 nm is highlighted with a red line.

Figure 12 compares the results of the displacement calculated with and without the substrate for a pillar of 45 nm in radius and 1.2 μm in height (left) and for a pillar of 45 nm in radius and

D2.1 – Report on relation deformation-force for the nanopillars

1.8 μm in height (right). There is a clear discrepancy between the two simulations that becomes smaller with increasing pillar height. The difference for the 1.2 μm tall pillar is around 12.4% while the difference for the 1.8 μm tall pillar is 8.6%. Additionally, the pillars on top of a larger substrate exhibit a larger displacement than the standalone pillars, with a fixed base. The simulations with the substrate allow the silicon oxide top surface surrounding the pillar to also move freely, which explains the discrepancy.

Figure 12. Maximum displacement for a pillar of 45nm in radius with a height of 1.2 μm and 1.8 μm (left and right respectively)

3.4 Silicon anisotropy

The anisotropy of Silicon Young's modulus (see Annex 1) results in a difference in pillar displacement depending on the direction of the applied force. The pillar displacement as a function of the angle of the applied force is shown in Figure 13 for a pillar 1200 nm tall and 45 nm in radius under an applied force of 15 nN (blue curve) and of 30 nN (red curve). The difference between the maximum and minimum values is about 23%, which is quite significant. Therefore, further simulations should also account for the silicon anisotropy.

Figure 13. Pillar displacement as a function of bending angle for two different force magnitudes (15 nN and 30 nN)

3.5 Pillar stress

When the pillar bends, the material experiences stress that could result in pillar breaking, if it is too large. We have therefore modelled the von Mises stress under bending.

The von Mises stress is a value used to determine if a given material will yield or fracture. If the von Mises stress of a material under load is equal or lower than the yield limit of the same material under simple tension, then the material will yield. For monocrystalline silicon, the tensile strength is about 2 GPa and the maximum strain is 1.2 % before fracture⁶.

We used the pillar on substrate simulation (panel c of Figure 2) to calculate the maximum stress experienced by the pillar, as we consider that this is the most realistic situation. As can be observed in Figure 14, this was unsurprisingly found to be at the base of the pillar.

Figure 14. Spatial distribution of the von Mises Stress around the base of the pillar.

Figure 15 shows the maximum von Mises stress for a variety of forces, pillar radii and pillar height.

The stress is inversely proportional to the pillar radius and proportional to both applied force and pillar height. For the simulated pillars shown in Figure 15 the stress values are well under the limit of 2 GPa except for some regions explored in pillars below 65 nm of radius (top left panel). Indeed, if we further calculate the stress for a 45 nm radius pillar with a height of 1.2 μm , then the stress starts approaching the fracture limit for applied forces above 35 nN, where the maximum displacement at the pillar top also approaches 100% of the pillar radius.

⁶ Tsuchiya, T. "Tensile testing of silicon thin films." *Fatigue & fracture of engineering materials & structures* 28.8 (2005): 665-674.

D2.1 – Report on relation deformation-force for the nanopillars

Figure 15. Maximum von Mises stress for different pillar dimensions and applied forces

We can therefore conclude that the pillar should not fracture under the expected forces, but that we must be cautious with further increasing pillar height.

4 Conclusions and future work

In this report, we have looked at the bending of nanopillars when a force in the nN range is applied to the tip of the pillar. We have seen that there are suitable combinations of heights and radii where the deformation is large enough to expect a response from a photonic crystal cavity. This response will be simulated in the near future.

In general, taller and thinner pillars bend more than shorter and thicker pillars, but the bending can also be improved by changing the material of the pillar (e.g., by making a composite pillar).

Nanopillar horizontal displacements larger than 10 nanometers are expected for forces in the range of nano Newton, pillars radii below 50 nanometers and pillar heights above 1 micrometer, (see Table below).

Therefore, the sensing area of the eventual photonic crystal sensors should be formed by nanopillars fulfilling the previous geometrical requirements while the body of the photonic crystal must be preferably composed of pillars with radii exceeding 80 nm to prevent meaningful modifications of the photonic crystal bandgap.

We have also seen that the anisotropy of silicon changes the relationship between the applied force and the deformation, with a variation of up to 23% as a function of the direction of the applied force. This variation in deformation must be considered in the design strategies for the nanosensors in the coming months.

Future work will reveal other limitations and considerations for the design of the nanosensor, such as restrictions in pillar dimensions limited by the optical properties, material choices limited by the biocompatibility, and pillar geometry limited by fabrication considerations.

The results and simulation models presented in this report are a starting point to implement a meaningful fabrication strategy of the devices envisaged in the project concept. These results have been shared among the project participants and will be used to assess the mechanical feasibility of future design ideas.

Radius (nm)	Height = 400 nm	Height = 800 nm	Height = 1200 nm	Height = 1800 nm
45	0.6	4.7	15.8	53.2
75	0.08	0.6	2.1	6.9
155	0.006	0.04	0.1	0.4

Table 2. Displacement in nm for three selected pillar radii and four pillar heights at an applied force of 15 nN

Glossary

Abbreviation	Explanation
DX	Deliverable X
F	Force
N	Newton (Force Unit)
Pa	Pascal (Pressure Unit)
Si	Silicon
WP	Work package

Annex 1: Anisotropy of Silicon

For a nanopillar etched into a (100) silicon substrates, Young's modulus (E) as a function of the bending direction (θ) is given by⁷

$$\frac{1}{E} = s_{11} - 2 \left[(s_{11} - s_{12}) - \frac{1}{2} s_{44} \right] (m^2 n^2)$$

Where s_{11} , s_{12} and s_{44} are material specific elastic constants (7.68 pPa, -2.14 pPa and 12.6 pPa, respectively), and m and n are the direction cosines of the chosen θ .

We have theoretically calculated Young's modulus for angles between 0 and 360 degrees.

This can be seen in Figure 16 as a polar plot. Here the radius of each circle has a value in GPa, while the angle is plotted around the circle. We can see that Young's modulus varies between 130 GPa and 170 GPa.

Figure 16. Polar plot of the Young's modulus of silicon as a function of bending angle.

⁷ M. A. Hopcroft, W. D. Nix, and T. W. Kenny, "What is the Young's Modulus of Silicon?," *J. Microelectromech. Syst.*, vol. 19, no. 2, pp. 229–238, Apr. 2010, doi: [10.1109/JMEMS.2009.2039697](https://doi.org/10.1109/JMEMS.2009.2039697).

